

THE WAYS OF HOW TO INCREASE LISTENING SCORE IN IELTS

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SAFARMURODOVA MAFTUNA
TERMIZ STATE UNIVERSITY 3rd course

Annotation: *This article is devoted to all the discussion of the role of importance among learners based on reading strategies and comprehension. This article presents different strategies, keys and examples as well.*

KEY WORDS: *semi-technical, source, ways, skills, General English, Academic English, methods, development, homework.*

General English is a semi-technical term for a course in English, usually as a mother tongue or in an English-medium school, within a framework of general education, usually teaching listening, speaking, reading, and writing. English for General Purposes (EGP) is called 'TENOR- the teaching of English for No Obvious Reason' (Abbot, 1981 in Jordan, 1997, p. 4). The title applies to those English language learning contexts where learners have no easily recognizable reason to learn the language. Learners should develop effective reading and writing skills in English. They work with information, ideas and opinions. They analyse and evaluate opinions and ideas. There are some differences between General English and Academic English. Academic English is very pertinent, which is set up to meet the specific needs of the learners. The teaching aims between the two are different. General English is the purpose of the examination, in addition to language learning without any purpose, so general English is also called basic English.

There are some ways of how to develop General English. You should do any reading homework or listening tasks. Initially, you should watch English movies, listen English music, reading English stories or books. You can actually develop your English level by these.

To tell the truth, there are two main problems in preparing for IELTS listening: one of the worst mistake is that students have a lack of awareness of how to develop the listening skills needed in the test and the second is the use of materials that do not reflect the real test. If students solve these problems, they can actually will be able to manage.

There are some exercises to develop listening skills:

1. Listen and say
2. Listen and explain
3. Listen and read

4. Listen and write

1. Listen and say

When you listen for any length of time, you tend to gradually stop paying attention. Knowing that you will need to repeat the information you hear trains you to stay focused and actively listen. This exercise also helps to develop your ability to recall what you have heard.

Listen to a very short extract and repeat what you hear. Listen several times if necessary, then check with the tapescript to make sure you got it right. As your skills develop, do the same with longer extracts (complete sentences if possible) and gradually move on to section 3 and 4 recordings. You will find this more difficult with the higher-level recordings, where both the information and the language are more complex.

If you struggle to do this, it may be because your brain is not 'decoding' what you hear. In other words, your brain hears a chunk of language and cannot separate this into the individual words being used. You will understand this problem better when we look at chunking in the speaking chapter. If you find this exercise too difficult, go back and work with passages from sections 1 and again, and build up your skills more gradually, or you can experiment with slowing down the recording. However, this may also be a sign that you need to focus on building your vocabulary and grammar skills first.

2. Listen and explain.

Listen to a slightly longer extract and then try to give the same information in your own words. This helps to test how much you understand. If you do not have to study partner to work with record yourself and listen again later to see how accurately you were able to explain the information. Gradually increase the length of the extracts you use to see how much of the information you are able to recall and summarise in this way

3. Listen and read

Rather than just using the tapescript and questions to check answers, you can also use them to train yourself to concentrate for longer periods, such as when following a discussion or talk. The Official Cambridge Guide to IELTS has several exercises to help practise recognising even more aspects of spoken language like this.

In fact, if it is impossible to do this with a recording and questions you have found, this is a good sign that you are using listening materials that do not reflect the real test.

4. Listen and write

Listen to a short extract and try to write down what you hear. Do this with section 2 and section 4 talks to practise keeping track. Pause the recording or repeat it as often as necessary. You can do this in two ways:

1) To test your ability to decode the words you are hearing, write down exactly what you hear, word by word. The benefit of this form of dictation is that it can help you to identify gaps in your own language: the words or phrases you miss and do not hear.

2) To test your understanding, as you listen write notes in your own words. As this is what the test questions do, it is good practice for recognising paraphrase, and will also help train you to keep track in the test.

Another important way of how to increase is learning new vocabularies and working on synonyms. For example, the word teach has got a lot of synonyms. You will be heard the word "teach". But in the question textbook you will be given such educate, indoctrinate, instruct, lesson, train, tutor and so on.

Children should pay attention to what the audio is about. If you can concentrate well, you will find all the answers easily.

Having effective listening skills means being able to display interest in the topic discussed and understand the information provided. In today's society, the ability to communicate effectively is becoming increasingly important. Although the ability to speak effectively is a highly sought-after skill, developing effective listening skills is often not regarded in the same respect.

In fact, listening is just as important as speaking. Being a good listener helps solve problems, resolve conflicts, and improve relationships. In the workplace, effective listening contributes to fewer errors, less wasted time, and improved accuracy. Effective listening helps build friendships and careers.

Five ways to improve your listening skills:

1. Face the speaker and give them your attention

It is tough to talk to someone who is constantly looking around. Make sure to face the speaker, eye contact, and give them undivided attention. In Western cultures, eye contact is necessary for effective communication. Although shyness, uncertainty, or cultural taboos may inhibit eye contact, try your best to make sure the speaker knows that they have your full attention.

2. Keep an open mind

Do not judge or mentally criticize what the speaker is telling you. Doing so can compromise your ability to take in what is being said. Never exhibit judgmental behavior, as it compromises your effectiveness as a listener. You can evaluate what was said after the speaker is finished talking, but don't do so while you are still listening to them.

Let the speaker finish what they are saying and don't be a sentence-grabber. Interrupting the speaker or prohibiting them from finishing what they are saying can indicate disrespect to the speaker. Often, interrupting the speaker mid-sentence interrupts their train of thought and can easily destroy a productive conversation.

3. Active listening

Active listening shows the speaker that you're interested and is an important business communication skill. Using active listening techniques helps to ensure that you correctly understand what is said.

Active listening techniques:

Paraphrasing back to the speaker what was said, to show understanding

Nonverbal cues (nodding, eye contact, etc.)

Verbal affirmations (“I understand,” “I know,” “Thank you,” etc.)

Demonstrating concern and establishing rapport

4. Just listen!

Create a mental model of the information, whether it be a picture or an arrangement of abstract concepts. Listen to keywords and phrases and do not rehearse what you are going to say after the speaker is done talking. Think about what the other person is saying rather than what you are going to respond with. It is difficult to think of what you are going to say while also listening to the speaker. Be attentive and relaxed – don't get distracted by your own thoughts and feelings.

The Importance of Listening:

Effective listening is a skill that is frequently undervalued in our society. Good communication skills require both effective speaking and listening. By being an attentive listener, you can understand more and improve relationships.

Make sure to:

Maintain eye contact and face the speaker to give them your attention

Don't be judgmental while listening

Don't interrupt the speaker

Employ active listening techniques

Think about what the other person is saying and not what you should respond with.

All in all, if students do the same way as following tips, without any doubt they can increase their score.

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